

Australian Research Data Commons

Best practices: PIDs for Instruments

Version 2

Identifiers for Instruments Australasia (i4iOZ)

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Text & infographics only.

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Acknowledgments

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Contributors

Siobhann McCafferty (ARDC), David Poger (University of Sydney), Yvette Wharton (University of Auckland), Christopher Seal (University of Auckland), Robin Burgess (ARDC), Erin Kenna (CSIRO), Fei Yu (University of Queensland), Angus Nixon (AUScope)

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Purpose

Instruments are essential to the activity of research, and there is a growing need to accurately describe and identify instruments digitally using a globally unique digital Persistent Identifier (PID). The purpose of this document is to explore use cases and outline best practices for assigning PIDs to research instruments. This document is an output of the Identifiers for Instruments in Australasia Community of Practice (i4iOZ). It has been revised in light of international and locally evolving practices and technical developments.

Rationale

PIDs facilitate the linking of research components (e.g. instruments, data, people, organisations, funding, projects) with outputs (e.g. metadata, publications, data sets, software, workflows, calibrations). Potential benefits that may arise from better linkage include:

- Metrics that quantify the use of instruments and the rationale for future funding
- Improved connection between data outputs and the instruments that generated them
- Facilitation of interoperability and open data sharing, especially in advancing technologies that foster sharing of instruments
- Improved discoverability and visibility of instruments and their data, published on the web
- Improved reproducibility of scientific results
- Support of appropriate authentication and access to sensitive data
- Improved tracking/locating of systematic errors generated by an individual instrument in a dataset/data collection, particularly where a survey has used several instruments/sensors.

These best practices recognise that there are a variety of definitions for an instrument. This document recognises that an instrument may be any and all of the following:

- A single instance of a tool, sensor or a device
Eg: [3T-magnetom-prisma](#)
- A sensor or individual measuring component on a single, complex instrument
Eg: The 9kW Cu rotating anode source (component of the Rigaku Smartlab above)
- A network, system or group of separate instruments that may be co-located or geographically distributed in space, but are connected through a single observation epoch

Eg: collections of sensors at moorings and reference stations or multiple sensors on an instrument platform such as sondes or gliders.

<https://www.csiro.au/en/about/facilities-collections/MNF/Research-vessel-Equipment-Data/Deployable-Equipment/CTD>

This document recognises that the definition of an instrument is likely to be domain-specific.

Scope

This document takes as essential background the recommendations of the Australian National Persistent Identifier (PID) Strategy and Roadmap, which was released in 2024 and identified five priority PIDs:

1. ORCID for identifying researchers and contributors to research
2. ROR for identifying research organisations and facilities that are part of the research ecosystem
3. DOI for identifying research grants, data, publications, instruments and other types of research outputs in scope for the DOI service provider
4. RAiD for identifying research projects and activities
5. IGSN for identifying physical samples for research

Identifier	Identifies	Service/organisational body responsible
ORCID	researchers and contributors to research	AAF/Australian Orcid Consortium
ROR	research organisations and facilities that are part of the research ecosystem	ROR
DOI	research grants, data, publications, instruments and other types of research outputs in scope for the DOI service provider	ARDC DOI service via DataCite
RAiD	research projects and activities	ARDC RAiD Service
IGSN	physical samples for research	ARDC DOI Service/ IGSN e.V

This document also draws on the work of the international community via the Research Data Alliance [PIDs for Instruments \(PIDINST\) Working Group](#) and the NSF-funded [FAIR Facilities and Instruments Research Coordination Network](#) in the United States.

The i4iOZ best practices should be read in conjunction with the [recommendations of the Research Data Alliance FAIR for Software Working Group](#), the recommendations of the [FAIR Facilities and Instruments Research Coordination Network](#) and the Research Data Alliance (RDA) Persistent Identifiers for Instruments Working Group [Metadata Schema](#)

The recommendations in this document cover best practices for:

- Base-level technologies
- Calibration data¹

These best practices are drawn from use cases provided by members of i4iOZ. Specific use cases come from:

- Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO)
- The University of Auckland – Waipapa Taumata Rau
- Microscopy Australia
- The University of Queensland
- The University of New South Wales (UNSW Sydney).

Best Practice Recommendation:

DOI

The recommended PID for individual instrument description is a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). There are various DOI Registration Agencies available globally that research organisations can use to mint DOIs. We recommend using DataCite as the Registration Agency.

The current DataCite Metadata Schema (version 4.6) has a [general Resource Type: Instrument](#)
`<resourceType resourceTypeGeneral="Instrument">Reflectometer</resourceType>`

The ability to mint a DOI for an instrument will depend on the relationship that each institution has to a DOI Registration Agency such as DataCite. For example, in Australia ARDC is the Consortium Lead for DataCite DOIs for the Research Community. Therefore Instrument DOIs

¹ Haller, A., Janowicz, K., Cox, S. J. D., Lefrançois, M., Phuoc, D. L., Lieberman, J., et al. (2019). The Modular SSN Ontology: A Joint W3C and OGC Standard Specifying the Semantics of Sensors, Observations, Sampling, and Actuation. *Semantic Web*, 10(1), 9–32.
<https://doi.org/10.3233/SW-180320>

may be registered using DataCite infrastructure (both a web interface and an API are available) through the [ARDC's DataCite DOI service](#), which is provided free of charge to Australian research universities, institutes and organisations.

Alternatively, organisations can join DataCite directly.

Versioning and Updating DOIs

Best practice is to use versioning with instruments, but the details of how this is to be managed is to be determined on a case-by-case basis in accordance with the host institution's standard practice.

The [Datacite DOI documentation on versioning](#) provides a good guide for this practice.

Where the DOI was minted using pre Schema 4.6 a new DOI may be minted. Specific advice is available via [PIDINST](#).

Landing Page/ Discovery

- An instrument PID must resolve to a landing page, which contains a description of the instrument or a link to a description of the instrument. Landing pages improve discovery. (Please see [FAIR guidelines](#) for more information).
- The landing page description of the instrument should be in a standardised format that takes into account the [current](#) DataCite Metadata Schema 4.6. Discovery of the instrument may be via an organisational repository or similar.
- Repository metadata may be harvested into [Research Data Australia](#) or similar for discovery purposes. A PID should return a machine-readable response for these purposes.

Metadata

- i4iOZ recommends describing instruments using the [PIDINST Schema](#), which aligns with the DataCite Metadata Schema.
 - Where a crosswalk or similar is needed, please refer to the [DataCite Mapping](#) resources
- Calibration data for instruments can be stored appropriately and identified by a Handle due to its working data nature. (See REF²) or a DOI if intended for sharing and publication.

² Haller, A., Janowicz, K., Cox, S. J. D., Lefrançois, M., Phuoc, D. L., Lieberman, J., et al. (2019). The Modular SSN Ontology: A Joint W3C and OGC Standard Specifying the Semantics of Sensors, Observations, Sampling, and Actuation. *Semantic Web*, 10(1), 9–32. <https://doi.org/10.3233/SW-180320>

- For example, a calibration report may be stored in a file that is given a Handle and noted in the instrument record
- Modifications and maintenance of an instrument should be recorded as appropriate to the discipline.
- For Australian organisations, Handles may be minted via the [ARDC Handle service](#).

Alternative identifiers

Handle

Where it is not possible to mint a DOI, a [Handle](#) should be used via the [ARDC Handle Service](#)

Note: Handles are not currently picked up by citation indexers

Research Resource Identifiers ([RRIDs](#))

RRIDs are global Persistent Identifier with origins in the Biomedical field and can be used for model-level, off-the-self generic instruments, but not for individual, physical instances of instruments.

RRIDs are not currently included in the ARDC Five Priority PIDs.

Use Cases

Regularly updated use cases can be found at the [i4iOZ Resources page](#).

Glossary

[FAIR](#)

[CARE](#)

[DOI](#)

[Handle](#)

[RAID](#)

[Research Data Australia](#)

[Research Data Alliance](#)

References

- [Best Practices: PIDs for Instruments \(1.0\)](#)
- [PIDINST white paper](#)
- [Persistent Identification of Instruments](#)
- [OGC SensorML standard](#)
- [Recommendations Toward a Framework for Adoption and Use of Persistent Identifiers for Research Facilities, Platforms, and Instruments](#)

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CONTACT

- ardc.edu.au
- +61 3 9902 0585
- contact@ardc.edu.au

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